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Paper-based microfluidic electro-analytical device (PMED) for magneto-assay automation: towards generic point-of-care diagnostic devices.

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Abstract

Rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) for point-of-care (POC) testing of infectious diseases are popular because they are easy to use. However, RDTs have limitations such as low sensitivity and qualitative responses that rely on subjective visual interpretation. Additionally, RDTs are made using paper-bound reagents, which leads to batch-to-batch variability, limited storage stability and detection of only the analytes they were designed for. This work presents the development of a versatile technology, based on short magneto-assays and inexpensive paper-based microfluidic electro-analytical devices (PMEDs). PMEDs were produced locally using low-cost equipment, they were stable at room temperature, easy to use, and provided quantitative and objective results. The devices served to detect alternatively a variety of magneto-assays, granting quantitation of streptavidin-HRP, biotinylated HRP and *Plasmodium falciparum* lactate dehydrogenase (Pf-LDH) in less than 25 min, using either commercial or customized screen-printed electrodes and measurement equipment. Furthermore, Pf-LDH detection in diluted lysed whole blood displayed a linear response between 3 and 25 ng·mL⁻¹, detection and quantification limits ranging between 1-3 ng·mL⁻¹ and 6-12 ng·mL⁻¹, respectively, and provided results that correlated with those of the reference ELISA. In short, this technology is versatile, simple, and highly cost-effective, making it perfect for POC testing.

Keywords: Malaria point-of-care testing, Magneto-immunoassay, Electrochemical biosensor, Paper-based diagnostic device, Screen-printed electrodes (SPE), Assay automation.

1 Introduction

Infectious diseases influenced wars, made empires fall, and shaped societies throughout the ages, having a significant impact in human history (Piret and Boivin, 2021). The advent of antibiotics and vaccines represented significant milestones in the battle against these scourges. Nonetheless, the mutable distribution of emerging and re-emerging infectious diseases, the rising notifications of multi-drug resistant bacteria, or the unusual recurrence of global pandemics, remind us of the threat of pathogens to human health. It is widely accepted that the combination of climate change and the global exchange of people and goods are contributing to the spreading of infectious diseases and their vectors (Baker et al., 2022). Malaria, an infectious disease caused by a parasite of the

genus *Plasmodium*, was responsible for 619,000 deaths and 247 million infections worldwide in 2021 (WHO et al., 2022), most of them in Africa. Nevertheless, a total of 2377 malaria cases were reported in the European Union (EU) in 2020, at least 5 of them locally acquired (3 in France and 2 in Greece) (ECDC et al., 2023). Yet, those numbers were substantially lower than in previous years due to the reduction in travel during the COVID-19 pandemic: >8200 malaria cases were reported annually in the period 2016-19, and 9 events of local malaria transmission were confirmed in Germany, Greece, Spain, France, and the Netherlands just in 2019.

In this context, access to accurate point-of-care (POC) diagnosis, data sharing and centralized management are critical for patient outcome and global public health (Kozel and Burnham-Marusich et al., 2017). According to the ASSURED criteria accepted by the WHO in 2003, POC tests should be affordable, sensitive, specific, user-friendly, rapid and robust, equipment-free, and deliverable to end-users. The recent developments have increased the need to guarantee also real-time connectivity, ease of sample collection and environmental friendliness, resulting in the REASSURED criteria (Land et al., 2019). In this scenario, rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) are excellent tools for POC testing of infectious diseases but display limitations (Shirshahi and Liu et al., 2021). RDTs require centralized fabrication using paper-bound reagents, which impels batch-to-batch variability, limited storage stability and detection of only the analyte they were produced for. Most RDTs exhibit also insufficient sensitivity to identify mild and asymptomatic infections, and provide a qualitative response that depends on subjective visual interpretation and is not easy to store.

Although electrochemical biosensors are often purported as an alternative to RDTs, most examples rely in the use of immuno-modified electrodes that display limited inter-device reproducibility and long-term stability, and that, again, detect only the analyte they were produced for. When operated in clinical samples, these may also present interference by electroactive species, such as uric and ascorbic acids, which can increase the background signal, and nonspecific adsorption of non-target components, like fatty acids and irrelevant proteins, which decreases the sensitivity and specificity of the biosensor (Wilkirson et al., 2023). In contrast, in electrochemical magneto-assays the bioassay is carried on magnetic beads (MB) and only detection is carried at bare electrodes of enhanced performance (Ahmadi et al., 2021; Herrasti et al., 2016). Magneto-assays have been reported to detect many biomarkers, including *Plasmodium falciparum* histidine rich protein (HRP-II) and pan-*Plasmodium* lactate dehydrogenase (pLDH), with limits of detection in the pg to low ng mL⁻¹ (Tables S1 and S2). However, magneto-assays

usually involve multiple incubation and washing steps using magnets, which demands for a certain level of user expertise and condition automation to the use of sophisticated platforms (Zhang and Nguyen, 2017).

We recently showed that magneto-assays can be partly automated using extremely simple paper-based devices (K. Arias-Alpizar et al., 2022a; Kevin Arias-Alpizar et al., 2022b). Our aim in the current work is to demonstrate the versatility of this technology, which takes advantage of the high performance of magneto-assays, the easy handling provided by paper devices, and the quantitative readout that characterizes biosensors. If we previously showed that the system was compatible with result colorimetric and fluorescent interpretation, we now implement electrochemical detection. For this, we develop a paper-based microfluidic electro-analytical device (PMED), which includes a paper-based device and a screen-printed electrode assembled into a 3D-printed holder. Next, we show that the system affords detection of 3 interchangeable magneto-assays, providing handling resembling that of RDTs and delivering quantitative, objective and manageable results in all the cases. Finally, we demonstrate that the system is compatible with the analysis of whole blood clinical samples, using alternatively commercial and customized screen-printed electrodes and measurement equipment, with results comparable to those of a reference ELISA. Furthermore, PMEDs were fabricated locally using low-cost equipment, were stable at room temperature, and performed well in the whole battery of assay and measurement set-ups tested. These results demonstrate that the technology reported is extremely versatile, simple and cost-efficient, in line with the requirements of POC testing and the REASSURED criteria, and highly compatible with the production of generic paper-based POC devices useful in a range of applications.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Biocomponents, Buffers and Reagents

Recombinant Pf-LDH was provided by CTK (San Diego, USA). Monoclonal capture and detection antibodies to pLDH (C01834M and C01835M, cMAb and dMAb, respectively) were from Meridian (Memphis, TE, USA). The latter were biotinylated (bt-dMAb; Supplementary information). Carboxylic acid MB (MyOne, 1 μm), Sera-Mag Streptavidin MB (Strep-MB, 0.85 μm), biotinylated horseradish peroxidase (bt-HRP; Ref. 432040), streptavidin-conjugated polymerized HRP (polyHRP, Ref. 21140), and 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) were from Thermo Fisher (Waltham, USA). Streptavidin-conjugated HRP (strep-HRP, Ref. ab210901) was from

Abcam (Cambridge, UK). Bovine serum albumin (BSA), Triton X-100, Imidazole 1 M, Tween 20, 3,3',5,5'-Tetramethylbenzidine Liquid Substrate System (TMB; Ref. T0440, including TMB and H₂O₂ at undisclosed concentration), and 2-(N-morpholino)ethanesulfonic acid hydrate (MES) were from Merck (Madrid, Spain). Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) was 10 mM sodium phosphate, NaCl 140 mM, KCl 2.7 mM, pH 7.4. Reagent Diluent (10XRD, Ref. DY995; equivalent to 10X PBS, 10% BSA) was from R&D (Abingdon, UK). PBST indicates PBS with 0.05% Tween 20; PBS-BSA indicates PBS with BSA 1%, prepared by diluting 10xRD; and PBST-BSA combines both. Washing solution was made of PBS supplemented with 0.1% Tween 20 (PBST_{0.1%}).

2.2 Screen printed carbon electrodes (SPCE)

Commercial SPCEs displayed a 4 mm disk graphite working electrode (12.6 mm²), a silver reference and a graphite counter electrode (Ref. DRP-110, Metrohm Dropsens, Oviedo, Spain). Before used, they were washed with 70% ethanol using a soft brush, rinsed with water, dried at room temperature, and characterized by cyclic voltammetry in 0.1 M KCl, 1 mM K₄Fe(CN)₆.

Customized SPCE featuring graphite working (2.5 mm, 4.9 mm²) and auxiliary electrodes, and a silver pseudo-reference, were fabricated as described elsewhere (Alba et al., 2021) (Supplementary information).

In both cases, SPCE were used for a single measurement and were discarded afterwards.

2.3 Standard Magneto-assays.

2.3.1 MB modification

Carboxylated MB were modified to incorporate either biotin (bt-MB) or cMAb (cMAb-MB) (Figure 1b and Supplementary information) and were stored in PBST-BSA_{0.2%} at 4°C until used. Such cMAb-MB were stable at 4°C for at least 2 months (Figure S1).

2.3.2 Magneto-assays for detection of bt-HRP and strep-HRP.

While bt-HRP was detected with strep-MB, detection of strep-HRP was performed using bt-MB. In both cases, serial dilutions of the corresponding enzyme were prepared in 100 µL PBST-BSA. It followed addition of MB to the samples (20 µg), a 10-min incubation (25°C, 950 rpm, in the dark) and two serial washings with PBS-T_{0.1%}.

2.3.3 Single-step sandwich magneto-immunoassay for detection of Pf-LDH

Serial dilutions of Pf-LDH protein were prepared in PBS-BSA. Said dilutions were incubated for 10 min at 950 rpm and 25°C with 75 ng·mL⁻¹ of bt-dMAb, 50 ng·mL⁻¹ of polyHRP and 20 µg of cMAb-MB in a final volume of 110 µL. The MB were then washed twice with 150 µL of PBS-T_{0.1%}.

2.3.4 Magneto-assay detection

For colorimetric detection, MB were resuspended with 100 µL TMB and incubated for 20 min at room temperature protected from light. MB were then concentrated using a magnetic rack, the supernatant was transferred to the wells of a microtiter plate, 50 µL of 2 N H₂SO₄ were added, and absorbance was measured at 450 nm in a FLUOstar Omega plate reader (BMG Labtech, Ortenberg, Germany).

For electrochemical detection, MB were resuspended with 50 µL of TMB and were transferred to a SPCE with a magnet below the working electrode (Figure 1c). Current was then recorded for 300 sec at -0.05 V (vs. Ag) using either a µStat 8000 multi-potentiostat (Metrohm Dropsens) or a customized hand held potentiostat. This low-cost and low-power equipment was designed for this application using off-the-shelf components (Figure S2). It had a user-friendly software interface, AmpVIEW, that controlled the system in real time to set-up the measurement and the format of the output data files (Montes-Cebrián et al., 2019)

2.4 Magneto-assays using the PMED

The magneto-assays described above included washes and detection carried manually. The PMED was produced to facilitate these steps.

2.4.1 PMED components and assembly

The PMED included a single-piece paper device, produced on Standard 17 (Ref. 8134-6621; Cytiva, Freiburg, Germany) using a Silhouette Cameo 3 cutting machine (Silhouette America, Lindon, USA), and an absorbent pump cut on CF5 (Ref. 8151-6621, Cytiva) with a guillotine (Figure 1d, top). Each PMED was assembled in a magnetic holder, designed using FreeCAD software and created with polylactic acid using a 3D printer (BCN3D Sigma). Once in the holder, the central section of the paper device sat on top of the 3-electrode electrochemical cell of a SPCE, which displayed similar diameter to facilitate alignment, and a magnet was allocated under the SPCE working electrode. A reagent reservoir, produced with a pipette tip, was pasted with Blu-Tack at

one end of the paper device. The pump was piled and fixed on the other end of the paper device. In this way, the paper device was secured onto the magnetic holder and did not move when solution was added. Each SPCE, paper device, and pump was used only once. For a schematic view of the PMED system, see Figure 2.

2.4.2 PMED-based magneto-immunoassay for Pf-LDH detection

Figure 1. Outline of the general methodology. a) Reagents key. b) Conjugation of MB with cMAb using EDC. c) One-step sandwich magneto-immunoassay carried in tubes and measured electrochemically. d) (top) Assembly of the PMED and (bottom) partial automation of the assay by carrying the washing steps and electrochemical measurement on-chip. 1, transfer of sample and reagents mixture after the 10-min incubation; 2, addition of washing buffer; 3, addition of substrate solution.

The PMED-based magneto-immunoassay involved sample/Pf-LDH incubation for 10 min with cMAb-MB, bt-dMAb and polyHRP in a tube. This mixture was pipetted directly to the central section of the paper device (Figure 1d, bottom). Here, a magnet concentrated the MB, and thus cMAb-MB/Pf-LDH/bt-dMAb/polyHRP complexes. Washing solution was immediately added to the reservoir (435 μ L twice). The advancing washing buffer washed the MB, while pushing the excess of reagents and sample components towards the pump. Finally, 50 μ L of TMB were deposited directly on the central section of the paper device and current was recorded at -0.05 V (vs. Ag). A total of six sensors were simultaneously measured using a multipotentiostat.

2.5 Whole blood clinical samples

This study had been approved by the Ethics Committee of Vall d'Hebron University Hospital (PR(AG)30/2018) and informed consent was obtained from all participants. Malaria patients and healthy individuals were recruited over 2018-2020. Peripheral blood samples were obtained in heparin collection tubes before the administration of antimalarial drugs. Malaria acute infections were confirmed by microscopy and/or by a WHO-endorsed commercial PCR. Blood samples were diluted 1:2 with lysis buffer (50 mM KH_2PO_4 300 mM NaCl, 0.25 M imidazole, 1% triton), were incubated for 5 min to release intra-erythrocytic parasites, were aliquoted and were then stored at -80°C (de la Serna et al., 2021).

2.6 Data analysis

Experiments were performed at least 3 times. Plots show means of no less than 3 independent replicates and the error bars correspond to one standard deviation.

Signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) refers to the quotient between the signals recorded for each positive and the average of the negative controls.

The limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) were calculated using the equations $LOD = \bar{x} + 3 \cdot \sigma$ and $LOQ = \bar{x} + 10 \cdot \sigma$, where \bar{x} is the average of the negative controls and σ their standard deviation.

3 Results and discussion

We showed previously that single-step magneto-assays could be partly automated using an extremely simple paper device, which allowed quantitative result interpretation by either colorimetry or fluorescence using a smartphone and a customized hand-held reader, respectively (K. Arias-Alpízar et al., 2022a; Kevin Arias-Alpízar et al., 2022b). Here, we assemble such paper devices with disposable SPCEs to produce simple, economical and versatile generic paper-based microfluidic electro-analytical devices (PMED), showing that they facilitate the operation and quantitative detection of different electrochemical magneto-assays. For this, we first optimize three single-step electrochemical magneto-assays for detection of bt-HRP, strep-HRP and Pf-LDH, and we compare their performance when carried in tubes or with the PMED. Then, we

demonstrate that PMEDs can be assembled using alternatively commercial and customized SPCEs. Next, we achieve electrochemical detection using both commercial and customized potentiostats. Finally, we afford malaria diagnosis in clinical blood samples. As it will be shown, PMEDs performed well in all the scenarios tested, which demonstrates the versatility of this technology.

3.1 Production of the PMED devices

PMEDs were designed to implement MB washing and electrochemical detection on-chip (Figure 2b). Essentially, this prototype consisted of a base made of ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) with an embedded magnet (Figure 2a I). Two pieces of transparent acetate were attached on top. The first featured a rim to accommodate a SPCE; and the second retained the SPCE in place. A paper microfluidic device was placed in the base, above the SPCE (Figure 2a II). This included three different reaction sections, separated by narrower channels. MB were retained in the central circular area, which was aligned over the SPCE 3-electrode cell (Figure 2a III) and above the magnet. At one end, a lanceolate section directed flow towards the central zone for MB washing. To facilitate this task further, a cylinder made from a pipette tip was glued with a Blu-Tack ring. This fixed the paper device to the base and served as a reservoir of washing buffer (Figure 2a IV). The other end of the paper device was subjected between the base and a piece of absorbent that functioned as a microfluidic pump and store for test residues (Figure 2a V-VI). This pump was initially held in place with an elastic band (Figure 2b). Later on, the whole system was enclosed in a 3D-printed holder (Figure 2c) that displayed a cover with protruding rims that secured the position of all the components (Figure 2c-d).

Figure 2. PMED components and assembly. a) Unassembled PMED components. I) Base (3.0x7.1 cm) with embedded magnet (\varnothing 5 mm). II) Paper device (Standard 17). III) Commercial SPCE (1.0x3.5 cm). IV) Reservoir with capacity for 500 μ L washing solution. V) Elastic band. VI) Paper pump (CF5; 3.0x2.4 cm) with a capacity of 800 μ L. b-d) Assembled PMED alone (b) or in the 3D holder open (c) or closed (d).

Best MB confinement was achieved using a 5-mm diameter magnet, which was slightly bigger than the 4-mm working electrode (Figure S3). Smaller magnets produced MB multi-layer crowding and bigger magnets retained part of the MB beyond the working electrode, worsening magneto-immunoassay electrochemical detection.

The geometry of the paper device had been previously optimized for magneto-immunoassay colorimetric detection (Kevin Arias-Alpizar et al., 2022b) and required minor re-optimization here to measure electrochemically. The key factor was the size of the circular section used for MB magnetic retention (Figure S4). This had to be large enough to cover the three electrodes of the SPCE to guarantee electrical contact during detection (7.5 mm in diameter), but not bigger to minimize MB dispersion and promote their concentration above the working electrode.

3.2 Electrochemical magneto-assays for detection of strep-HRP, bt-HRP and Pf-LDH at SPCEs

We started by optimizing two different model magneto-assays in which strep-MB and bt-MB were applied to detect bt-HRP and strep-HRP, respectively (Figure 3a-b). In both cases, enzyme capture was followed by MB washing in tubes, MB resuspension in TMB substrate solution and transfer to a bare SPCE with a magnet attached below for electrochemical detection.

The results of the electrochemical detection of both magneto-assays are displayed in Figure 3d-e. As it can be observed, bt-MB displayed liner response for strep-HRP concentrations up to 100 ng mL⁻¹, while strep-MB produced signal saturation for bt-HRP above 10 ng mL⁻¹. This difference was partly attributed to the use of two HRP variants of different commercial origin and composition, and partly to the fact that each streptavidin on the MB surface could bind more than one bt-HRP molecule.

Figure 3. Magneto-bioassay electrochemical detection at SPCEs. a) Strep-HRP detection with bt-MB. b) Detection of bt-HRP with Strep-MB. c) Sandwich magneto-immunoassay for Pf-LDH detection. d-f) Calibration plots obtained for a-c when detected electrochemically at bare SPCEs using TMB substrate.

A third magneto-assay was optimized for Pf-LDH detection based in a previous development (Figures 3c, S4) (Ruiz-Vega et al., 2020). This included a single incubation

of the sample with a cocktail of 3 reagents: cMAb-MB, polyHRP, and bt-dMAb. After immunocapture, the MB were washed on a rack with magnets, TMB enzyme substrate was added and the mixture was transferred to a SPCE for electrochemical detection (Figure 1c).

The optimal concentrations of polyHRP and bt-dMAb in the assay were determined by testing concentrations of polyHRP from 25 to 200 ng·mL⁻¹ and concentrations of bt-dMAb from 37.5 to 300 ng·mL⁻¹ (Figure S5). Although the currents registered increased with the amount of polyHRP and bt-dMAb used in the assay, the background noise increased as well. The best results were obtained using 50 ng·mL⁻¹ of polyHRP and 75 ng·mL⁻¹ of bt-dMAb, which generated the highest S/N ratios.

In the same way, larger numbers of cMAb-MB apparently producer higher signals but generated also larger background noise and complete coverage of the working electrode. This presumably hindered the diffusion of TMB to/from the solution and the electrochemical detection of low Pf-LDH concentrations (Figure S6). The optimal amount of cMAb-MB per sample was of 20 µg, making the assay as efficient but more cost-effective than higher concentrations of cMAb-MB.

When measured directly on a bare SPCE, this sandwich magneto-immunoassay displayed linear response for Pf-LDH concentrations up to 50 ng·mL⁻¹, an LOD of 1.2 ng·mL⁻¹ and an LOQ of 5.8 ng·mL⁻¹.

3.3 Handling and detection of the magneto-assays using the PMED

The operation of the magneto-assays using the paper device is illustrated in Figure 1d. The assay started with a single 10-min incubation of the sample (containing bt-HRP, strep-HRP or Pf-LDH) with the corresponding cocktail of reagents (strep-MB in the first case; bt-MB in the second; and c-MAb-MB, polyHRP and bt-dMAb in the third), which was carried in a tube. The mixture was then transferred to the washing pad of the paper device. Washing buffer was added to the device reservoir, which pushed the excess of sample and reagents across the retention zone, where the MBs (and thus strep-MB/bt-HRP, bt-MB/strep-HRP, or c-MAb-MB/Pf-LDH/d-MAb/polyHRP complexes in positive samples) were trapped magnetically. Finally, the PMED was connected to a potentiostat, 50 µL of TMB enzyme substrate were added to the central area, and current was recorded for 300 seconds at -0.05 V (vs. Ag).

Detection of bt-HRP and strep-HRP at the PMED produced, on average, currents 3 times lower than those registered for similar concentrations directly at SPCEs (Figure S7). This showed that only part of the enzyme captured or the enzyme product produced was detected efficiently in the PMED. Nevertheless, the trends registered resembled those observed previously on bare SPCEs. This is, while strep-HRP displayed linear response over the whole range of concentrations tested (up to 50 ng mL⁻¹), bt-HRP produced higher signals and signal saturation above 10 ng mL⁻¹.

For Pf-LDH detection in lysed whole blood, the washing steps needed additional optimization to ensure that (1) the volume of washing buffer was large enough to remove all cell debris and reagent excess from the MB retention zone before detection; (2) this volume was absorbed completely by the pump to avoid reagent reflow; and (3) the whole system was solution-saturated so that TMB addition created a nearly static measurement cell in which TMB did not flow away over detection. For the volume of sample and reagents used (110 µL), a volume of 870 µL was selected, which was pipetted to the reservoir in two successive additions (435 µL each; Figure S8). PBS-T_{0.1%} yielded the best S/N ratio out of the different washing solutions tested (Figure S9).

Despite optimizing the working and washing buffers, the background noise in the PMEDs was higher than that in the tube-based assay. This effect was attributed to non-specific adsorption of the test reagents (especially polyHRP) on the paper-based device. To reduce background noise, paper devices were blocked by immersion in PBS-BSA_{5%} for 15 min, then rinsed in PBST, dried at 37°C for 1 h and stored at room temperature for up to 3 months before their use (Figure S10; longer storage time not tested).

Finally, the magneto-immunoassay immunocapture was extended from 5 to 10 min to improve Pf-LDH detection, which improved the signal and S/N registered (Figure S11).

Figure 4a shows the calibration plots obtained with the PMED in PBST-BSA and lysed whole blood diluted to different extents. The background noise increased proportionally to the concentration of blood and the LOD/LOQ worsened accordingly. Although most Pf-LDH concentrations tested were detected in blood 1:20, the LOD/LOQ worsened compared to the values obtained in PBST-BSA (Figure 4b). In contrast, the calibration curves obtained for 1:50 and 1:100 blood dilutions were very similar to the one in PBST-BSA, with comparable LOD and LOQ (around 3 and 10 ng mL⁻¹, respectively). This corresponded to an LOD spanning between 30 and 300 ng mL⁻¹ of Pf-LDH in prediluted blood (for samples analysed 1:10 and 1:100, respectively), which matched the range of

LODs observed for the existing RDTs that detect this protein (10–1000 ng mL⁻¹) (Jimenez et al., 2017)

Figure 4. Performance of the PMED in spiked blood. a) Signals registered for different concentrations of Pf-LDH spiked in either PBST-BSA or whole blood (diluted 1:2 with lysis buffer and then 1:10, 1:25 and 1:50 with PBST-BSA to final dilutions 1:20, 1:50 and 1:100). b) LOD and LOQ of the calibrates in “a”.

Previous studies had reported concentrations of Pf-LDH between 7 and >3000 ng·mL⁻¹ in malaria patients (de la Serna et al., 2021). Thus, the results suggested that the PMED could detect the concentrations of Pf-LDH displayed by patients with medium-to-high parasitemias in less than 25 min, with sensitivity and level of handling comparable to the commercial rapid devices available for malaria diagnosis, but producing quantitative results. Furthermore, the proposed device exhibited LOD similar to that in (Ruiz-Vega et al., 2020) but was easier to produce, achieved Pf-LDH quantitation comparable to similar paper devices detected colorimetrically or fluorescently in previous works (K. Arias-Alpizar et al., 2022a; Kevin Arias-Alpizar et al., 2022b), and detected Pf-LDH comparably or better than most examples in Table S1. The present device was also faster and easier to use.

3.4 Evaluation of technology versatility and performance in clinical samples

We next studied if the technology was robust and versatile enough to support Pf-LDH detection in clinical samples using alternatively commercial and customized SPCE and measurement equipment.

Figure 5 shows the two types of SPCE compared in the PMED and the calibrates obtained for Pf-LDH detection in both cases. The currents registered for customized SPCEs were lower than those obtained for commercial SPCE due to the smaller size and higher hydrophobicity of the working electrodes (2.5 and 4 mm, respectively). Customized SPCE displayed also lower background noise in the negative controls and slightly more sensitive Pf-LDH detection in spiked blood (LOD/LOQ of 2.1/6.3 and 3.2/12.8 ng·mL⁻¹ for customized and commercial SPCE, respectively; Figure 5b), which improved the S/N (Figure S12).

Lysed blood samples obtained from malaria patients were next analysed using alternatively PMEDs with both types of SPCE. The quantification of Pf-LDH provided by both PMED systems correlated to each other and to that granted by the reference ELISA (Figure 5c). This demonstrated that the paper device could be successfully coupled in the PMED with different measuring SPCE.

Figure 5. Detection of Pf-LDH in spiked and clinical samples using commercial or customized SPCEs in the PMED. a) Commercial and customized SPCEs used. b) Signals registered for increasing Pf-LDH concentrations spiked in blood (lysed and diluted 1:50) using commercial and customized SPCEs. c) Plot of the concentrations of Pf-LDH ($\text{ng}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) detected by the reference ELISA and the PMED with commercial and customized SPCE in four clinical samples (lysed and diluted 1:50), obtained by interpolation of the currents registered in the corresponding calibrate in “b”. (Insert) Concentrations detected in the samples with the reference ELISA (orange bars) and the PMED using commercial (blue) or customized SPCE (green). Each sample was analysed thrice independently, each time with a new PMED.

PMEDs were finally measured using a low-cost miniaturized USB-powered potentiostat. This platform measured 10.5 x 5.8 x 2.5 cm, weighed 41 g, and had a manufacturing cost of approximately 85 USD (Figure 6a; (Montes-Cebrián Y, Álvarez-Carulla A, Ruiz-Vega G, Colomer-Farrarons J, Puig-Vidal M, Baldrich E, 2019)). It included three main components: a power module that provided stable voltage and negative supply, a front-end module containing dual-supply potentiostats, and the back-end module, comprising a microcontroller and a LabVIEW-based GUI, enabling easy operation on any computer.

Figure 6. Detection of Pf-LDH in spiked and clinical samples using commercial and customized potentiostats to measure the PMED. a) Customized USB-powered hand-held potentiostat. b) Signals registered in the PMED for increasing concentrations of Pf-LDH spiked in lysed blood 1:50 (red) and in PBST-BSA (blue) using commercial and customized (POC-USB) potentiostats. c) LOD and LOQ for each sample medium (lysed blood 1:50 and PBST-BSA) and potentiostat. d) Plot of the concentrations of Pf-LDH detected by the PMED measured by a commercial and the POC-USB potentiostat versus those obtained by the reference ELISA in six clinical samples.

As shown in Figure 6b, PMED-based Pf-LDH quantification was efficient in similar concentration ranges independently of the potentiostat used, both in PBST-BSA and lysed blood 1:50. The customized equipment generated in general lower signals and lower S/N (Figure S13), but also lower background noise and LOD/LOQ (Figure 6c). A set of clinical samples was finally studied with the PMED (Figure S14) and the two measurement set-ups, and the concentrations of Pf-LDH measured were contrasted to those obtained using the reference ELISA (Figure 6d). The numbers obtained with the PMED correlated well with those of the ELISA, independently of the potentiostat used, and the results provided by the two potentiostats correlated with each other as well.

Once more, the results demonstrated the viability and versatility of the cost-effective PMED platform developed, enabling the operation and detection of magneto-assays independently of sophisticated equipment and installations.

4 Conclusions

In this work, we developed a versatile and adaptable platform for electrochemical detection of magneto-assays. By exploiting generic paper-based microfluidic devices, PMEDs achieved partial automation of different magneto-assays, with a level of handling comparable to that of RDTs, but providing quantitative, reproducible and storable readouts. Detection of Pf-LDH for diagnosis of malaria infection took less than 25 min, and displayed linear response between 3 and 25 ng·mL⁻¹, LODs of 1-3 ng·mL⁻¹ and LOQs of 6-12 ng·mL⁻¹ independently of the type of SPCE and electrochemical reader used. Furthermore, Pf-LDH quantitation in clinical samples was comparable for all the PMED set-ups tested and, in all cases, correlated with the standard ELISA, exhibiting versatility and adaptability for each measuring disposition. When compared to previous examples, PMEDs displayed LOD that matched those of commercial RDTs for Pf-LDH detection, faster and simpler handling than the magneto-assays reported previously (Tables S1 and S2), and unprecedented versatility.

By now, PMEDs achieve partial automation of magneto-assays, incorporating on chip washings and electrochemical detection, but also an external incubation of the sample with a cocktail of reagents. Future development should target complete assay automation, such as by incorporating interchangeable reservoirs with preloaded reagents, to facilitate handling further without compromising platform versatility. The LOD/LOQ and long-term stability of the different components should be enhanced as well. Nonetheless, these results show that it is possible to produce generic paper devices that could detect different bioassays through diverse transduction formats. Such a diagnostic kit format should facilitate that users store at room temperature the bulkiest kit components (the paper-based devices), or even produce them locally on demand, to use them over time for detection of the different magneto-assays needed. This would in turn result in less need for refrigerated space, lower losses due to disposal of unused expired devices, and faster response for detection of different pathogens.

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Paper-based microfluidic electro-analytical device (PMED) for magneto-assay automation: towards generic point-of-care diagnostic devices.

Supplementary information.

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Tables

Table S1. Magneto-assays reported previously for malaria detection.

Table S2. Works having exploited previously magnetic particles as biosensing platforms for electrochemical detection in fields other than malaria detection.

Material and Methods

1. Fabrication of customized screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCE)

Customized SPCE were fabricated at BCMaterials (Basque Center for Materials, Applications and Nanostructures. UPV/EHU Science Park, 48940 Leioa, Vizcaya, Spain).

Customized SPCE featuring graphite working (2.5 mm diameter, 4.9 mm²) and auxiliary electrodes, and a silver pseudo-reference electrode, were fabricated as described elsewhere (Alba et al., 2021). Briefly, silver tracks and pseudo-reference electrode were printed on PET substrates from MacDermid Autotype (Wantage, UK) using a 90 threads cm⁻¹ mesh screen (Paymser, Cerdanyola, Spain) and Loctite EDAG 725A Silver paste (Tetrachim, Noisiel, France). This was cured in a convection oven at 120°C for 20 min, after which the graphite electrodes were printed using a 77 threads cm⁻¹ mesh screen and GST4500 PTF Graphite paste (Sun Chemicals/Servilan, ES). This was cured in a convection oven at 120°C for 30 min. Last, the dielectric (Loctite EDAG 455B, Tetrachim) was screen printed through a 90 thread cm⁻¹ mesh screen and cured in under Flood UV lamp for 45 sec.

Before cutting the electrodes, the working graphite electrode was laser-treated in air using a 30W CO₂ laser (Epilog Mini 18, Laser Project, Barcelona, Spain) set to dose an energy of 12.8 mJ·cm⁻², equivalent to 15% power and 50% speed raster settings at 600 dpi in our system. Laser treatment removes surface binder and amorphous carbon, leaving only highly crystalline graphite behind (Alba et al., 2022). This new surface behaves as highly ordered pyrolytic graphite.

2. Production of biotinylated detection antibodies (bt-dMAb).

The detection antibody (dMAb) was first submitted to a buffer interchange. For this, 300 µg of d-MAb were placed in an Amicon Ultra 0.5 mL Centrifugal Filter (Merk Millipore) in a final volume of 0.5 mL. The device was centrifuged at 14000 x g for 10 min, was filled with 0.5 mL of sodium carbonate buffer (0.1 M, pH 9.5), was centrifuged again, and the whole procedure was repeated once more. The concentrated dMAb was then recovered, and sodium carbonate buffer was added to bring it to a concentration of 4 mg·mL⁻¹.

A stock of biotin-XX, SSE (6-((6-((Biotinoyl)Amino)Hexanoyl)amino)Hexanoic Acid, Sulfosuccinimidyl Ester, Sodium Salt; Ref. B6352, ThermoFisher Scientific) was prepared at a concentration of 2.5 mg·mL⁻¹ in water and 9.66 µL were added to the dMAb. The mixture was stirred at 24°C in the dark for 2 h. Unbound biotin was eliminated

using a PD G25 exclusion column (GE Healthcare) following the provider's instructions. The bt-dMAb obtained in this way was finally diluted to a concentration of $150 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ in PBS 1X and was stored in working aliquots at -20°C .

3. MB modification with biotin or with cMAb

For modification with biotin, carboxylated MB ($100 \mu\text{L}$, equivalent to 1 mg) were washed twice with $100 \mu\text{L}$ of MES (15 mM , $\text{pH } 6.0$) using a magnetic separator. MB were then pre-activated with EDC ($2 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ in $100 \mu\text{L}$ of MES) for 15 min at 950 rpm in a thermoshaker (Ref. 460-0249P, VWR). Then followed two serial washes with MES and incubation for 2 h with biocytin $2.5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ in a rotator (Ref. LA-H5500, Labnet). After washing with MES first and PBS next ($200 \mu\text{L}$ each), MB were blocked with PBS-BSA for 1 h at 950 rpm . After washing twice for 5 min with $100 \mu\text{L}$ of PBST, the biotinylated MB (bt-MB) were resuspended in 0.5 mL of PBST supplemented with BSA 0.2% (PBST-BSA $_{0.2\%}$) for storage at 4°C .

Modification of carboxylated MB to incorporate cMAb had been optimized previously in (Ruiz-Vega et al., 2020). Briefly, MB ($100 \mu\text{L}$, equivalent to 1 mg) were washed twice with MES. MB were then incubated at 950 rpm for 15 min , in $100 \mu\text{L}$ of MES with $25 \mu\text{g}$ of cMAb and EDC at $2 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$. MB were next serially washed with MES and PBS ($200 \mu\text{L}$ each), and were blocked for 1 h with $100 \mu\text{L}$ PBS-BSA. Conjugated MB (cMAb-MB) were washed twice for 5 min with $100 \mu\text{L}$ of PBST and were resuspended in 0.5 mL of PBST-BSA $_{0.2\%}$ to be stored at 4°C until used (Figure 1b).

Results

Figure S1. Conjugated magnetic beads stability.

Magnetic beads modified with cMAb (cMAb-MB) were stored at 4° and evaluated over time. For this, serial dilutions of Pf-LDH protein were prepared in PBS-BSA. Said dilutions were incubated for 10 min at 950 rpm and 25°C with 75 ng·mL⁻¹ of bt-dMAb, 50 ng·mL⁻¹ of polyHRP and 20 µg of cMAb-MB in a final volume of 110 µL. Beads were then washed, TMB substrate added and detection carried. The evaluation concluded that, at least for this cMAb and conjugation procedure, the modified cMAb-MB were stable for at least 2 months if stored at 4°C in PBST-BSA_{0.2%} without any preservative added.

Figure S2. Fabrication of customized potentiostat

The custom potentiostat consists of a back-end and a front-end fully custom designed for this application using off-the-shelf components. The back-end is implemented using a module based on a Texas Instruments MSP430FR5969. This family of microcontrollers is characterized by its ultra-low power requirements. On the other hand, the front-end is a fully specialized design for this application making use of ultra-low-power off-the-shelf components. The application requires very low bias currents and frequencies. This allows the choice of ultra-low power components that normally have low current source capability and low bandwidth. Thus, the adhoc electronics is capable of operating with the sensor with a limit of detection of $0.05 \mu\text{A}$, limit of quantification of $0.07 \mu\text{A}$, maximum consumption of 6.215 mA for the back-end and $235 \mu\text{A}$ for the front-end, weight of 41 g , and a cost of 85 USD . The device stands out in terms of power consumption (autonomy), weight (portability) and cost compared to other commercial solutions without detriment to its specifications as a measurement instrument. The schematics of the custom potentiostat is presented next and additional specifications can be found in (Montes-Cebrián et al., 2019).

(Left) Block diagram of the full-custom potentiostat and (Right) picture of the developed prototype: (Top) full-custom PCB (cooper board) and MCU board (red board). (Bottom) Detail of the custom software AmpVIEW (Montes-Cebrián et al., 2019). Creative Commons license© 2019 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Figure S3. Effect of magnet size in MB distribution over the working electrode and magneto-immunoassay electrochemical detection.

A selection of magnets of different dimensions was tested to determine which retained better the MB onto the working electrode of a SPCE and how MB magnetic confinement affected magneto-immunoassay electrochemical detection.

The magnets tested are shown in **a)** and displayed sizes of, from left to right, 4x1.5 mm, 5x1.5 mm, and 10x4 mm (diameter x width). Magnets were attached below the working electrode of the SPCE using adhesive tape, the SPCE were cantilevered and 50 μL of PBS containing 0.4 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$ (20 μg) of MB were pipetted onto the electrodes. As it can be observed, the magnets produced different MB dispersion over the working electrode surface. The 4 mm magnet (that displayed same size than the working electrode) generated the tightest MB packing, with MB multilayer assembly. In contrast, the 10 mm magnet generated wide and irregular distribution of the MB, which partly escaped from the working electrode surface. The 5 mm magnet, which was slightly bigger than the working electrode, presented the best performance, with MB distributed homogeneously and reproducibly across the working electrode, and was thus selected.

Graphs **b)** and **c)** show that magnet size affected also the electrochemical detection of a magneto-immunoassay, with highest assay sensitivity (slope) and S/N obtained when using the 5 mm magnet for Pf-LDH assay detection.

Figure S4. Optimization of the design of the PMED paper device

The paper device was designed to carry MB concentration and washing on-chip, removing the excess of sample and assay's reagents before assay detection.

The paper device was cut using a Silhouette craft cutter on a paper-like glass fibre membrane (Standard 17, ref. 8134-6621; Cytiva Europe GmbH, Freiburg, Germany). The design of this paper device had been optimized in a previous work (Arias-Alpizar et al., 2022b), to provide whole blood washing and prevent interference of the blood components in magneto-immunoassay colorimetric and fluorescent detection. The chip included three different sections, separated by narrower necks. A lanceolate section, on one end, facilitated the washing of MB under flow conditions and directed flow towards the central zone. MB were retained in this central area, which was circular in shape. At the other end, another circular section accommodated the absorbent pads.

Here, the central section was redesigned to facilitate magneto-immunoassay electrochemical detection. Three different designs were tested, which displayed central sections ranging between 5 and 10 mm in diameter that provided different coverage of the SPCE electrochemical cell. The optimal one was the 7.5 mm, which had the smallest circle that granted complete coverage of the 3 electrodes, providing as well lower MB dispersion than bigger features.

Figure S5. Optimization of the magneto-immunoassay for detection of Pf-LDH

This magneto-assay was optimized based in a previous development (Ruiz-Vega et al., 2020). In the original assay, the sample was incubated with cMAb-MB and polyHRP coupled to bt-dMAb. Because this polyHRP-bt-dMAb conjugate was stable for only a few weeks, here the assay was reoptimized to include incubation of the sample with a cocktail of 3 reagents that were stable separately: cMAb-MB, polyHRP, and bt-dMAb. In order to determine the optimal concentrations of polyHRP and bt-dMAb, increasing concentrations of Pf-LDH were detected using in parallel concentrations of polyHRP from 25 to 200 ng·mL⁻¹ and concentrations of bt-dMAb from 37.5 to 300 ng·mL⁻¹. The assays were carried in parallel in the absence of Pf-LDH to assess the background noise. Detection was carried colorimetrically, which allowed detecting more samples simultaneously than electrochemical detection. For this, after immunocapture and washing, MB were incubated with 50 μ L of TMB for 20 min, were concentrated in a magnetic rack, the supernatant was transferred to the wells of a microtiter plate, 50 μ L of acid were added and absorbance was measured at 450 nm.

As it can be observed, the signal registered increased proportionally to the concentration of polyHRP (a) and bt-dMAb (b) used in the assay, but the background noise increased as well. Accordingly, maximum S/N was observed for all Pf-LDH concentrations detected with 50 ng·mL⁻¹ of polyHRP (c). For the bt-dMAb, a plateau was reached just below 80 ng·mL⁻¹ (d).

Figure S6. Optimization of the concentration of MB in the magneto-immunoassay for detection of Pf-LDH

Determining the optimal concentration of cMAb-MB per sample was carried out by electrochemical analysis, since the sensitivity of the assay strongly depended on the distribution of MB on the working electrode.

In the magneto-immunoassay, it was expected that the greater the number of cMAb-MB used per sample, the greater the amount of potentially bound Pf-LDH and polyHRP, thus signal generated. However, the confinement of large amounts cMAb-MB on the working electrode could cover it completely, interfering in the diffusion of TMB from the solution and in its electrochemical detection.

As illustrated in figure a), the signal grew when by adding more MB to the sample, but higher background noise was registered as well. b) Although this did not seem to affect the detection of high Pf-LDH concentrations, this resulted in a decrease in S/N for low-to-mid Pf-LDH concentrations. Accordingly, more consistent, and higher S/N were obtained when using 20 μg of cMAb-MB per sample.

Figure S7. Electrochemical detection of bt-HRP and strep-HRP using the PMED platform.

Samples containing different concentrations of either bt-HRP or strep-HRP were incubated for 10 min with strep-MB or bt-MB in a tube. The mixture was then transferred to the washing pad of the paper device to carry MB washing and assay electrochemical detection on-chip. For this, washing buffer was added to the device reservoir. The washing buffer flowed along the paper device. While the MB (and thus strep-MB/bt-HRP or bt-MB/strep-HRP complexes in positive samples) were retained by the magnet in the central area, above the electrode, the excess of sample and reagents were pushed across the retention zone and towards the adsorption pad. The PMED device was then connected to a potentiostat, 50 μL of enzyme substrate TMB were added to the central area, and current was registered for 300 seconds at a -0.05V (vs. Ag).

In general, the current (a) and S/N (b) measured for the detection of bt-HRP using strep-MBs were 3-4 times higher than those obtained for the detection of strep-HRP at bt-MB. This could be partly attributed to the fact that each streptavidin molecule on the surface of strep-MB could capture between 1 and 4 bt-HRP, while only one strep-HRP molecule could be captured by each biotin on bt-MB. On the other hand, a similar weight concentration of bt-HRP and strep-HRP should display approximately double molar concentration of bt-HRP.

Figure S8. Optimization of the washes carried on-chip at the PMED.

a) In these experiments, 110 μL of whole blood, lysed and diluted 1:10 (1:2 initial dilution in lysis buffer and 1:5 dilution with PBS-BSA buffer), was pipetted in the center of the lanceolate section of the paper device. Next, 100-600 μL of washing buffer were dispensed into the reservoir. At least 200 μL of washing buffer were needed to remove the blood completely and leave the paper device visually clean. However, addition of TMB resulted in color evolution, suggesting that cell debris and/or cell components remained attached to the material (result not shown). Thus, wash volumes 500-800 μL were needed to grant low background noise. **b)** To better optimize PMED washing, volumes of washing buffer between 500-1000 μL were dispensed in the reservoir of the PMED (including paper device and the pump). Next, 50 μL of stained PBS were added and solution flow was observed over time. In devices having been washed with less than 800 μL of washing buffer, the stained solution flowed towards the absorbent pad. On the contrary, when washing with >900 μL , the absorbent pad was solution-saturated and the stained buffer was partly absorbed by the washing pad. Thus, the volume of washing buffer that provided saturation of the absorbent pad, granting a certain balance between absorption and reflux, was set between 800 and 900 μL . A volume at 870 μL was selected for subsequent experiments.

Figure S9. Selection of best-performing washing buffer for on-chip MB washing.

The single-step magneto-immunoassay was carried in the absence or in the presence of Pf-LDH (25 ng mL^{-1}). The mixture of reagents was next transferred in a PMED and MB washing was carried on-chip by adding $870 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$ of one of the following washing buffers: PBS- $T_{0.1\%}$ (PBS-T), PBS/PBS- $T_{0.1\%}$ ($435 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$ each, added one after the other), PBS 1X, PBS 0.1X, and MiliQ water. After the washing buffer had been adsorbed, TMB was added and the amperometric measurement was started. **a)** Currents and **(b)** S/N recorded for the positive and negative controls of Pf-LDH detection as a function of the wash solution. As depicted, PBS-T produced the highest current in the positive control and also the highest S/N.

Figure S10. Paper device stability.

To reduce background noise, paper devices were blocked by immersion in PBS-BSA_{5%} for 15 min, then rinsed in PBST, dried at 37°C for 1 h and stored at room temperature in sealed bags to be protected from ambient light and humidity. As is can be seen, compared to freshly prepared devices, the devices stored for a period of 3 months were stable and showed the same properties and performance. From this point, the paper devices turned yellowish and started shrinking. Addition of preservatives or vacuum packaging could be a solution for long-term stability, but further testing needs to be done.

Figure S11. Optimization of magneto-immunoassay incubation time for PMED detection.

One of the critical steps of the magneto-immunoassay was the incubation of all the assay reagents with the analyzed sample. To limit the overall assay duration without compromising its sensitivity, 3 incubation times were tested ranging from 5 to 15 min. Current signals for a positive and negative sample of Pf-LDH are presented in **a)** **b)** Although the S/N ratio between positive and negative samples was higher as the incubation time was extended, an incubation of 10 min was selected because it provided lower variability than shorter incubations but higher signal and nearly as high S/N as the 15-min incubation.

Figure S12. Pf-LDH detection using commercial and customized SPCEs in the PMED.

Commercial (4 mm ϕ) and customized (2.5 mm ϕ) screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCE) were used in the PMED to test the versatility and robustness of the system. Currents registered (a) and S/N data (b) obtained for the electrochemical detection of Pf-LDH under both experimental conditions.

Figure S13. Pf-LDH detection using commercial and POC-USB potentiostats in the PMED.

Commercial and customized (POC-USB) potentiostats were tested with the PMED platform. (a) Currents registered and (b) S/N data of the electrochemical detection of Pf-LDH for each calibration curve. In general, the commercial potentiostat displayed higher currents and S/N at middle-to-high Pf-LDH concentrations, but results were equivalent for both equipment at low concentrations of Pf-LDH.

Figure S14. Study of clinical samples positive (P) and negative (N) for malaria .

(a) Currents registered when analyzing clinical samples, positive (P) and negative (N) for malaria, with the PMED using commercial SPCE and potentiostat, and **(b)** the corresponding Pf-LDH concentration. The plots display the results of 3 independent replicates for each sample. The horizontal dotted line marks the analytical LOD calculated from the negative control samples. PMED

Table S1. Magneto-assays reported previously for malaria detection. “Assay steps” refer to incubations carried in tubes. Pf-LDH, Pv-LDH and pLDH stand for *P. falciparum*, *P. vivax* and pan-*Plasmodium* LDH; HRP-II, histidine rich protein; QD, quantum dots; QR, Quanta Red fluorescent HRP substrate. * CTK recombinant Pf-LDH of 64 kDa.

Assay format	Detection method	Target	Assay steps*	Assay time	Linear assay range	LOD	Samples	Ref.
Direct	Colorimetric	Pf-LDH	2	1 h 15 min	-	25.7 ± 1.1 pM	<i>P. falciparum</i> spiked whole blood	(Markwalter et al., 2016)
Direct	Colorimetry	Pf-LDH	1	2 h 30 min	-	0.01% parasitemia	10 patient samples <i>P. falciparum</i> & 10 <i>P. vivax</i>	(Fraser et al., 2018)
Direct	Fluorescent	HRP-II Pf-LDH Pv-LDH	6	15 h	0.007-0.763 ng mL ⁻¹ 0.008–17 ng mL ⁻¹ 0.008–17 ng mL ⁻¹	0.006 ng mL ⁻¹ 0.056 ng mL ⁻¹ 1.093 ng mL ⁻¹	2031 plasma, serum, EDTA whole blood	(Martíáñez-Vendrell et al., 2020)
Sandwich	Colorimetric	pLDH HRP-II	2	50 min 30 min	7.0-500 pM 1.5-80 pM	2.6 ± 1.5 pM 1.6 ± 1.0 pM	Commercial pooled human whole blood	(Markwalter et al., 2016)
Sandwich	Colorimetric	HRP-II	1	2 h 30 min	1.3 – 62.5 ng mL ⁻¹	1.31 ng mL ⁻¹	12 patient serum samples	(De Souza Castilho et al., 2011)

Sandwich	Colorimetric	HRP-II	4	1 h 30 min	Qualitative	1.0 parasite· μL^{-1}	<i>P. falciparum</i> spiked blood	(Fairhurst and Dondorp, 2016)
Sandwich	Fluorescent (QD)	Pf-LDH Pv-LDH	3	1 h 55 min	0.51-15 fmols	0.001 – 0.066 ng mL ⁻¹ (10 – 1000 amols)	-	(Kim et al., 2017)
Sandwich	Fluorescent (QD)	HRP-II	4	1 h 45 min	0.1-10 ng mL ⁻¹	Vial (0.1 ng mL ⁻¹) Droplet (2.5 ng mL ⁻¹)	-	(Kim et al., 2017)
Sandwich	Fluorescent (QD)	HRP-II	2	4 h	4-100 ng mL ⁻¹	0.5 ng mL ⁻¹	-	(Castro-Sesquen et al., 2016)
Sandwich	Colorimetric Fluorescent Chemiluminescent	Pf-LDH	2	10 + (20, 15 or 1) min	0.4-12.5 ng mL ⁻¹ 0.1-25 ng mL ⁻¹ 0.04-12.5 ng mL ⁻¹	0.12 ng mL ⁻¹ 0.11 ng mL ⁻¹ 0.02 ng mL ⁻¹	7 patient lysed whole blood samples	(Sánchez-Cano et al., 2021)
Sandwich (paper device)	Colorimetric (TMB) Colorimetric (QR) Fluorescent (QR)	Pf-LDH	1	20 min	3.1-50 ng mL ⁻¹ 1.56-50 ng mL ⁻¹ 0.78-12.5 ng mL ⁻¹	3.1 ng mL ⁻¹ (48 pM)* 1.56 ng mL ⁻¹ (24 pM)* 0.9 ng mL ⁻¹ (14 pM)*	9 patient lysed whole blood samples	(Arias-Alpízar et al., 2022)
Sandwich	Electrochemical	HRP-II	3	2 h	0.87 – 62.5 ng mL ⁻¹	0.87 ng mL ⁻¹	12 patient serum samples	(De Souza Castilho et al., 2011)
Sandwich (paper electrode)	Electrochemical	Pf-LDH	1	<20 min	6.25-100 ng mL ⁻¹	2.51 ng mL ⁻¹ (29 pM)*	3 patient lysed whole blood samples	(Ruiz-Vega et al., 2020)
Sandwich (PMED)	Electrochemical	Pf-LDH	1	25 min	3.12-25 ng mL ⁻¹	1.74 ng·mL ⁻¹ (27 pM)*	6 patient lysed whole blood samples	This work

Table S2. Works having exploited previously magnetic particles as biosensing platforms for electrochemical detection in fields other than malaria detection. CFU, colony-forming unit; IL-8, interleukin 8;

Assay format	Type of magnetic bead	Target	Assay steps	Assay time	Linear assay range	LOD	Ref.
Sandwich	180 nm MNB	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	3	1:30 h	$3 \cdot 10^1$ to $3 \cdot 10^4$ CFU mL ⁻¹	300 CFU mL ⁻¹	(Chen et al., 2015)
Sandwich	2.7 µm MB	IL-8 IL-8-mRNA	>5	3:30 h	0.69–7.5 nM 241.3–5000 pg·mL ⁻¹	0.21 nM 72.4 pg·mL ⁻¹	(Torrente-Rodríguez et al., 2016)
Sandwich	MNB	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	2	>1:30 h	$1.9 \cdot 10^3$ – $1.9 \cdot 10^6$ CFU mL ⁻¹	$1.6 \cdot 10^3$ CFU mL ⁻¹	(Wang et al., 2017)
Sandwich	2.8 µm MB	Shrimp tropomyosin	5	5 h	0.25-4.0 µg·mL ⁻¹	47 pg·mL ⁻¹	(Angulo-Ibáñez et al., 2019)
Sandwich	2.8 µm MB	Sola I 7 allergen	3	1:30 h	0.8 -50 pM	0.2 pM	(Pereira-Barros et al., 2019)
Sandwich	25 µm MB	<i>Ostreopsis cf. ovata</i>	4	overnight	0.1 – 2 ng·µL ⁻¹	9 pg·µL ⁻¹	(Toldrà et al., 2019)
Sandwich	1 µm MB	Pf-LDH	1	25 min	3.12-25 ng mL ⁻¹	1.74 ng·mL ⁻¹ (27 pM)*	This work

IL-8-mRNA, interleukin 8 messenger RNA; MNB, magnetic nanobead; MB, magnetic bead. * CTK recombinant Pf-LDH of 64 kDa.

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